

Simulation of the evolution of biomass burning organic aerosol with different volatility basis set schemes in PMCAMx-SRv1.0

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Abstract

A source-resolved three-dimensional chemical transport model, PMCAMx-SR, was applied in the continental U.S. to investigate the contribution of the various components (primary and secondary) of biomass burning organic aerosol (bbOA) to organic aerosol levels. Two different schemes based on the volatility basis set were used for the simulation of the bbOA during different seasons. The first is the default scheme of PMCAMx-SR and the second is a recently developed scheme based on laboratory experiments of the bbOA evolution.

The simulations with the alternative bbOA scheme predict much higher total bbOA concentrations when compared with the base case ones. This is mainly due to the high emissions of intermediate volatility organic compounds (IVOCs) assumed in the alternative scheme. The oxidation of these compounds is predicted to be a significant source of secondary organic aerosol. The impact of the other parameters that differ in the two schemes is low to negligible. The monthly average maximum predicted concentrations of the alternative bbOA scheme were approximately an order of magnitude higher than those of the default scheme during all seasons.

The performance of the two schemes was evaluated against observed total organic aerosol concentrations from several measurement sites across the US. The results were different for the different seasons examined. The default scheme performed better during July and

30 September while the alternative scheme performed a little better during April. These results
31 illustrate the uncertainty of the corresponding predictions, the need to quantify the emissions and
32 reactions of IVOCs from specific biomass sources, and to better constrain the total (primary and
33 secondary) bbOA levels.

34

35 **1. Introduction**

36 Over the past decades, atmospheric aerosols, also known as particulate matter (PM), are
37 at the forefront of atmospheric chemistry research due to their adverse impacts on human health,
38 climate change, and visibility. More specifically, fine particulate matter with an aerodynamic
39 diameter less than 2.5 μm ($\text{PM}_{2.5}$) is associated with decreased lung function (Gauderman et al.,
40 2000), bronchitis incidents (Dockery et al., 1996), respiratory diseases (Pope, 1991; Schwartz et
41 al., 1996; Wang et al., 2008) and eventually increases in mortality (Dockery et al., 1993). $\text{PM}_{2.5}$
42 also affects the planet's energy balance (Schwartz et al., 1996), and causes visibility reduction in
43 urban centers but also rural areas (Seinfeld and Pandis, 2006).

44 One of the most important components of fine PM almost everywhere is organic aerosol
45 (OA) (Andreae and Crutzen, 1997; Roberts et al., 2001; Kanakidou et al., 2005). Despite its
46 importance, OA remains poorly understood due to its physicochemical complexity (Goldstein
47 and Galbally, 2007). OA is traditionally separated into primary (POA), which is emitted directly
48 into the atmosphere as particles, and secondary OA (SOA), which is OA that is formed from
49 gaseous precursors that after oxidation and condensation form organic particulate matter
50 (Seinfeld and Pandis, 2006). SOA includes components produced during the oxidation of semi-
51 volatile organic compounds (called SOA-sv), of intermediate-volatility organic compounds
52 (SOA-iv), and of volatile organic compounds (SOA-v). POA and SOA are further categorized
53 into anthropogenic (aPOA, aSOA) and biogenic (bPOA, bSOA) based on their sources. The
54 terms POA and SOA (without a prefix for anthropogenic or biogenic) are used to denote the
55 totals, that is the sum of the anthropogenic and biogenic components. Also the term bbOA is
56 used for the sum of primary and secondary biomass burning OA ($\text{bbOA}=\text{bbPOA}+\text{bbSOA}$).

57 Biomass burning is an important global source of OA (Puxbaum et al., 2007; Gelencser et
58 al., 2007; Chen et al., 2017; Gunsch et al., 2018) and other pollutants such as nitrogen oxides,
59 carbon monoxide, and volatile organic compounds. This source contributes around 75% of
60 global combustion POA (Bond et al., 2004). In this work, the term biomass burning includes

61 wildfires in forests and other areas, prescribed burning which is a small wildfire set intentionally
62 (Tian et al., 2008; Chiodi et al., 2018) in order to decrease the likelihood of major wildfires,
63 agricultural waste burning, and residential burning.

64 The simulation of bbOA has been the topic of numerous studies all of them concluding
65 that it is an important source of fine particles (Tian et al., 2009). Most of them assumed that
66 bbOA is non-volatile and inert (Chung and Seinfeld, 2002; Kanakidou et al., 2005). Alvarado et
67 al. (2015) used the Aerosol Simulation Program that incorporates updates to the gas-phase
68 chemistry and SOA formation modules using observations from a biomass burning plume from a
69 prescribed fire in California. A method was presented for simultaneously accounting for the
70 impact of the unidentified intermediate volatility, semi-volatile, and extremely low volatility
71 organic compounds on the formation of OA, based on the volatility basis set (VBS) approach
72 (Robinson et al., 2007) for modeling OA and the concept of the mechanistic reactivity of a
73 mixture of organic compounds (Carter, 1994). Bergström et al. (2012) concluded that residential
74 wood combustion and wildfires are a major source of aerosol over large parts of Europe.
75 However, the simulated results are sensitive to the parameters used in the VBS framework.
76 Posner et al. (2019), using the standard version of PMCAMx, that incorporates the VBS scheme,
77 estimated that bbSOA from semivolatile and intermediate volatility organic compounds emitted
78 during biomass burning is one of the most important components of bbOA in the US.

79 Fountoukis et al. (2014) performed simulations in Europe using the PMCAMx model
80 during 2008-2009. The largest discrepancies of average PM_{10} OA concentrations between model
81 and measurements were found during the winter. Ciarelli et al. (2017a, b) proposed an alternative
82 parameterization that was derived from biomass burning experiments conducted with emissions
83 from woodstoves, and was based on the VBS scheme (Koo et al., 2014). This alternative
84 parameterization was applied only to the residential heating sector. The applicability of this
85 parameterization to other biomass burning sources such as wildfires and prescribed burning will
86 be investigated in the present study. The alternative framework was evaluated using CAMx for
87 February – March 2009. The new scheme narrowed the difference between predictions and
88 observations compared to previous studies (Fountoukis et al., 2014), but still underpredicted the
89 observed SOA, whereas the bbPOA was generally overpredicted. The same scheme was
90 evaluated for 2011 in Europe using CAMx 6.3 (Jiang et al., 2019). The authors concluded that

91 the modified parameterization improved the model performance for total OA as well as the OA
92 components especially during the winter.

93 The aim of the current study is to implement the alternative VBS scheme proposed by
94 Ciarelli et al. (2017a, b) in the PMCAMx-SR model during different periods. These periods have
95 already been investigated by Theodoritsi et al. (2020) using the default PMCAMx-SR scheme.
96 That study concluded that during spring the PMCAMx-SR performance is good according to the
97 criteria proposed by Morris et al. (2005) but the model tends to underpredict the observed OA in
98 the PM_{2.5} size range. During the modeled summer period the PMCAMx-SR performance was
99 average with a tendency towards overprediction of the observed PM_{2.5} OA. Finally, during the
100 fall the model performance was average-to-problematic because the model overpredicted the OA
101 levels. The OA overprediction during this period was mainly due to the probable overprediction
102 of the bbOA (primary and secondary) which was according to the model the dominant OA
103 component. We aim to further investigate whether the application of this new parameterization
104 that has improved bbOA predictions in Europe will close the gap between predictions and
105 observations in the US too.

106 In most modelling studies so far biomass burning OA (bbOA) is grouped with the rest of
107 the primary and secondary OA components and is simulated in exactly the same way. In this
108 study, PMCAMx-SR the three-dimensional chemical transport model (CTM) used simulates
109 bbOA components separately from the rest of the OA allowing the use of volatility distributions,
110 aging schemes, etc. that are specific to this source (Theodoritsi et al., 2019). At the same time,
111 this enhanced model (extension of PMCAMx) allows direct predictions of bbOA concentrations
112 since it tracks these species separately. Theodoritsi et al. (2020) used PMCAMx-SR to quantify
113 the importance of bbOA from prescribed burning activities in the US on air quality and human
114 health.

115 In the current study we will study in detail the impact of the different partitioning
116 parameters implemented in bbPOA description and bbSOA formation and evolution as proposed
117 by Ciarelli et al. (2017a, b). While the previous study of Theodoritsi et al. (2020) focused on the
118 role of prescribed burning as a source of bbOA, in this study all biomass burning sources are
119 grouped together.

120

121

122 **2. The chemical transport model PMCAMx-SR**

123 PMCAMx-SR is a source-resolved version of the three-dimensional CTM PMCAMx
124 (Murphy and Pandis, 2009; Tsimpidi et al., 2010; Karydis et al., 2010). PMCAMx lumps all
125 anthropogenic OA components and biomass burning OA together, so it does not explicitly keep
126 track of their sources and by necessity uses source-independent parameterizations for the OA.
127 PMCAMx-SR uses different variables to describe the OA from different sources and therefore
128 allows the different treatment (e.g., volatility distributions, partitioning parameters like enthalpy
129 of vaporization, chemical aging schemes, etc.) of OA from on-road transportation and that from
130 biomass burning. Both PMCAMx and PMCAMx-SR simulate emissions, advection, turbulent
131 dispersion, removal by wet and dry deposition, chemistry in the gas, aqueous and particulate
132 phases and aerosol dynamics using the same computational modules. They differ in the treatment
133 of OA. Different gas-phase chemistry mechanisms can be selected by the user. In this study the
134 Carbon Bond 5 mechanism (Yarwood et al., 2005; ENVIRON, 2015) is used expanded for the
135 treatment of secondary organic aerosol production. The extended version of the mechanism used
136 simulates the concentrations of 103 gas-phase stable species and of 13 free radicals using 269
137 chemical reactions. The aerosol-size composition distribution is simulated using the sectional
138 method with eight size bins for the diameter range from 40 nm to 10 μm and two more for larger
139 sizes used for particles that have grown to cloud droplets. PMCAMx-SR in this study simulates
140 in total 67 aerosol components both inorganic and organic. PMCAMx-SR is flexible and its user
141 can select which OA source to treat independently of the others (biomass burning is selected
142 here) and also which OA parameterizations to employ.

143 **2.1 Simulation of organic aerosol (base scheme)**

144 PMCAMx-SR uses the VBS framework (Donahue et al., 2006; Stanier et al., 2008) for
145 the simulation of the various components of OA (as does PMCAMx). The VBS treats all primary
146 and secondary OA components as semi-volatile simulating their partitioning between the vapour
147 and particle phases. It also treats all of them as reactive allowing the simulation of both the initial
148 stage of formation of SOA but also later generations of reactions (often called “chemical aging”).
149 Volatility is expressed in the VBS using the effective saturation concentration at 298 K, C^* , and
150 the volatility distribution is split in logarithmically spaced volatility bins (differences of factors
151 of 10).

152 The emitted primary organic compounds include: volatile organic compounds (VOCs; C^*
153 $\geq 10^6 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$), intermediate volatility organic compounds (IVOCs; C^* bins of 10^3 , 10^4 , 10^5 , and
154 $10^6 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$), semi-volatile organic compounds (SVOCs; in the 1, 10, $100 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ C^* bins) and
155 finally low volatility organic compounds (LVOCs; $C^* \leq 0.1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) (Donahue et al., 2009).
156 PMCAMx-SR uses the generic POA volatility distribution proposed by Robinson et al. (2007) to
157 simulate the anthropogenic OA emissions from all sources except biomass burning. The total
158 VBS emissions are assumed to be 2.5 times the original non-volatile POA emissions in the
159 traditional inventory used for regulatory purposes (Robinson et al., 2007; Murphy and Pandis,
160 2009; 2010). This default volatility distribution in previous studies using PMCAMx was
161 implemented to all sources of OA including biomass burning.

162 In PMCAMx-SR, the fresh and secondary bbOA components are modelled separately
163 from the other OA components which are simulated with the default PMCAMx parameters. The
164 gas-particle partitioning parameters used for bbPOA species are the ones proposed by May et al.
165 (2013). However, the volatility distribution proposed in that study only includes compounds up
166 to a volatility bin of $10^4 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. The total emissions of the bbPOA components in the $0.1\text{-}10^4 C^*$
167 bins are assumed to be equal to the non-volatile bbPOA emissions in the traditional inventory.
168 Following the approach of Theodoritsi et al. (2020), the total emissions of the more volatile
169 IVOCs (C^* values of 10^5 to $10^6 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) are set equal to 0.5 times the original nonvolatile POA
170 emissions. Therefore, the total biomass burning organic emissions used in this study are 1.5
171 times the original POA emissions.

172 SOA from anthropogenic volatile organic compounds (aSOA-v) and SOA from biogenic
173 volatile organic compounds (bSOA-v) are represented by four volatility bins with C^* values
174 ranging from 1 to $10^3 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 298 K. Long-range transport OA (lrtOA) is assumed to be
175 heavily oxidized OA and is treated in PMCAMx-SR as nonvolatile and nonreactive. Overall, the
176 OA components included explicitly in PMCAMx-SR are: fresh primary anthropogenic OA
177 (POA), fresh primary bbOA (bbPOA), anthropogenic SOA from VOCs (aSOA), biogenic SOA
178 (bSOA), SOA from semi-volatile anthropogenic organic compounds (SOA-sv), SOA from
179 intermediate-volatility anthropogenic organic compounds (SOA-iv), bbSOA from semi-volatile
180 organic compounds (bbSOA-sv), bbSOA from intermediate-volatility organic compounds
181 (bbSOA-iv), and long-range transport OA.

182 All OA components (except from long range transport OA) are treated as chemically
183 reactive in PMCAMx-SR. The rate constant used for the chemical aging reactions with the OH
184 radical is the same as the one currently used for all primary organic vapors in the VBS and has a
185 value of $4 \times 10^{-11} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ molec}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. SOA-sv, SOA-iv, bbSOA-sv and bbSOA-iv components are
186 assumed to further react with OH radicals in the gas phase, resulting in the formation of lower-
187 volatility SOA and bbSOA components. All aSOA components are assumed to react with OH in
188 the gas phase with a rate constant of $1 \times 10^{-11} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ molec}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (Atkinson and Arey, 2003).
189 Chemical aging of bSOA (both homogeneous and heterogeneous reactions) is assumed to lead to
190 a small net change of mass and is neglected (Murphy and Pandis, 2010). All the aging reactions
191 mentioned above are assumed to take place only in the gas phase and to reduce the volatility of
192 the reacted vapor by one order of magnitude. These reactions are assumed to result in an increase
193 of the OA mass by 7.5% due to the added oxygen.

194 Table 1 summarizes the VBS parameters of all OA species in the base PMCAMx-SR
195 simulation. All POA and bbPOA components are assumed to have an average molecular weight
196 of 250 g mol^{-1} , aSOA components of 150 g mol^{-1} , while bSOA species of 180 g mol^{-1} . The
197 effective enthalpies of vaporization of both POA and bbPOA species are based on fits of diesel
198 and wood-smoke partitioning data (Lipsky and Robinson, 2006; Shrivastava et al., 2006).

199

200 **2.2 Alternative bbOA scheme**

201 The scheme of Ciarelli et al. (2017a, b) for the simulation of the emissions of organics
202 from residential heating biomass burning and their evolution in the atmosphere during winter
203 was also implemented in PMCAMx-SR. The organic PM emissions (assumed nonvolatile in the
204 original inventory) are distributed in this scheme across five volatility bins with saturation
205 concentrations values ranging from 10^{-1} and $10^3 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ following the volatility distribution and
206 enthalpy of vaporization proposed by May et al. (2013). Organic vapors in this volatility range
207 are assumed to react with OH forming semi-volatile oxidation products with an order of
208 magnitude lower volatility:

210 where i is the corresponding volatility bin, bbPOG_{*i*} is the primary emissions in the gas phase and
211 bbSOG_{*i*} are their oxidation products. Fragmentation processes are implicitly assumed to balance
212 the effect of the increase in oxygen content of the reacting molecules. Both schemes (base case

213 and alternative) do not simulate explicitly the functionalization and fragmentation reactions. The
214 alternative scheme of Ciarelli et al. (2017a, b) assumes that these two processes in a sense
215 balance each other leading to mass stoichiometric yield equal to unity in the corresponding net
216 reaction.

217 All emitted IVOCs in this bbOA scheme are assumed to have a C^* value of $10^6 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$
218 (Ciarelli et al., 2017a, b), which is at the high end of the IVOC saturation concentration range.
219 The emission rate of these IVOCs is assumed to be 4.75 times the primary OA emissions in the
220 original inventory. The IVOCs are assumed to react according to the following reaction:

221 $\text{bbPOG}_{10^6} + \text{OH} \rightarrow$

222 $0.143 \text{bbSOG}_{10^3} + 0.097 \text{bbSOG}_{10^2} + 0.069 \text{bbSOG}_{10^1} + 0.011 \text{bbSOG}_{10^0}$ (2)

223 yielding secondary products with saturation concentration ranging from $C^*=1$ to $10^3 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. In
224 this reaction bbPOG_{10^6} stands for the primary emissions in the volatility bin with C^* value equal
225 to $10^6 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$, whereas bbSOG_{10^3} to bbSOG_{10^0} are the secondary gas phase oxidation products of
226 the IVOCs with C^* values ranging from 10^3 to $10^0 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. For both primary and secondary
227 compounds aging is simulated assuming a gas phase reaction rate constant with OH of 4×10^{-11}
228 $\text{cm}^3 \text{ molec}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The lowest volatility secondary bbPOA components in this scheme have
229 $C^*=10^{-1} \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ since the $C^*=1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ species can react with OH to form lower volatility
230 products.

231 Table 1 also summarizes the volatility distribution, the molecular weights, and enthalpies
232 of vaporization of all bbOA species used in the alternative bbOA modeling scheme used in this
233 study. The enthalpies of vaporization used in this bbOA scheme are the ones proposed in Ciarelli
234 et al. (2017a, b). The structure of the VBS combined with the modular structure of PMCAMx-SR
235 allow the user to change easily the corresponding parameters (volatility distributions, enthalpies
236 of vaporization, aging scheme, etc.) and therefore change the OA parameterization for the source
237 of interest.

238

239 **3. Model application**

240 In this study PMCAMx-SR is used to simulate three seasonally representative months
241 (April, July, and September) during 2008 for the continental US. The modeling domain also
242 included southern Canada and northern Mexico. The first two days of each simulation were
243 excluded from our analysis to allow for model spin-up, but the corresponding results are shown

244 in time series plots. The modeling domain covers a region of 5328×4032 km² with 36×36 km
245 grid cell resolution and 25 vertical layers extending up to 19 km (Figure 1). An annual CAMx
246 simulation was performed for the same domain to obtain the necessary initial conditions used in
247 our simulations for each month (ENVIRON, 2013).

248 The Weather Research and Forecast Model (WRF) version 3.3.1 (NCAR, 2012) was used
249 to produce the meteorological inputs needed by PMCAMx-SR. The land-use data were based on
250 the U.S. Geological Survey Geographic Information Retrieval and Analysis System (USGS
251 GIRAS) database. The photolysis rate input data were produced by the NCAR Tropospheric
252 Ultraviolet and Visible (TUV) radiation model. The chemical boundary conditions were based
253 on simulations using the MOZART global CTM (Emmons et al., 2010). Additional details about
254 the model inputs can be found in Posner et al. (2019) and Theodoritsi et al. (2020).

255 The emission inventory used in the current study tracks separately the biomass burning
256 emissions from the emissions of other sources. The latter are based on the U.S. National
257 Emissions Inventory (2008 NEI). Biomass burning emissions include emissions of prescribed
258 burning, agricultural burning, and wildfires and the methods used for their estimation inventory
259 be found in WRAP (2013; 2014). The fire activity data used are described in Ruminski et al.
260 (2006), Eidenshink et al. (2007) and Mavko and Randall (2008). The approach used for the
261 preparation, processing, and validation of fire activity data were similar to those of Wiedinmyer
262 et al. (2006) and Raffuse et al. (2009). For fire consumption estimates CONSUME3 (Joint Fire
263 Science Program, 2009) was used for all biomass burning sources except agricultural burns for
264 which the method from the WRAP 2002 emissions inventory was employed (WRAP, 2005).

265 During all three examined periods based on the emissions inventories used biomass
266 burning was a significant POA source mainly in the Southeast U.S. (Posner et al., 2019;
267 Theodoritsi et al., 2020). Specifically, during April, July and September respectively this source
268 represents approximately 25%, 65% and 37% of the total POA emissions. During April 19% of
269 the domain-averaged bbPOA emissions rate are due to agricultural burning, 47% to prescribed
270 burning, and 34% to wildfires. During July, due to the very high wildfire emissions mainly in
271 northern California, the domain-averaged bbPOA emissions are mostly (96%) due to this source.
272 Agricultural burning contributed 1% and prescribed burning the remaining 3%. For September,
273 wildfires in the west were still the dominant source and they were responsible for 73% of the
274 domain bbPOA emissions. Prescribed burning was a significant source (22% of the bbPOA

275 emission), while agricultural burning was responsible for 5% of the emissions. Posner et al.
276 (2019) and Theodoritsi et al. (2020) have presented analysis of the spatial distribution and
277 magnitude of these bbPOA emissions.

278

279 **4. Predicted bbOA concentrations**

280 In this section the predictions of PMCAMx-SR for the base case and the alternative
281 bbOA scheme are analyzed. In this work bbOA is defined as the sum of primary (bbPOA) and
282 secondary (bbSOA) OA. The latter is the sum of bbSOA originating from semi-volatile organic
283 compounds (bbSOA-sv) and from IVOCs (bbSOA-iv). The small SOA contribution from VOCs
284 (Posner et al., 2019) is not explicitly accounted in the bbSOA, but is included in the aSOA and
285 bSOA simulated by the model. The results of the PMCAMx-SR simulations with the two
286 schemes are shown in Figures 1-3.

287 During April both schemes predict approximately the same bbPOA concentrations
288 (Figure 1) that were as high as $3.5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ on a monthly average basis in the southeastern US.
289 These high levels were mainly due to prescribed burning. The differences in predicted bbPOA
290 levels by the two models were less than $0.1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ (maximum difference in average levels) in all
291 areas of the domain (Figure 4) something expected given that they use the same volatility
292 distributions for the primary LVOCs and SVOCs. Predicted average ground bbPOA levels over
293 the US were approximately $0.02 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ (average of ground concentrations over the whole
294 domain). The domain and simulation average bbPOA values are quite low given that fires often
295 have a significant effect for only a few days for a limited area. These values are provided here
296 mainly to facilitate the comparison of the two parameterizations. The predicted bbSOA-sv
297 concentration fields were also quite similar (differences less than $0.1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) for the two schemes
298 (Figure 1). This is also the consequence of the similarity of the volatility distributions and
299 chemical aging parameterizations used by the two schemes in the SVOC volatility range of the
300 biomass burning emissions. While the average bbSOA-sv levels over the domain were quite
301 similar to those of the bbPOA (around $0.02 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$), the peak levels were lower with a maximum
302 monthly average concentration of $0.5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. This spreading of the bbSOA-sv further from the
303 fires is the result of the time needed for the corresponding reactions to take place. The
304 predictions of the two schemes are quite different though for bbSOA-iv (Figure 1). For the base
305 scheme, the bbSOA-iv is equally important as the bbPOA and the bbSOA-iv contributes on

306 average $0.02 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ of OA over the domain. The peak monthly average bbSOA-iv concentration
307 is predicted to be approximately $0.2 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in the southeast. The predictions for bbSOA-iv for
308 the alternative scheme are approximately an order of magnitude higher, with a maximum average
309 of $2 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and a domain average of $0.2 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ (Figure 1). Even if the IVOC emissions are
310 assumed to be more volatile in the alternative scheme, their high emission rate allows the
311 production of significant concentrations of secondary OA from biomass burning that extend over
312 the eastern half of the country during this photochemically active period.

313 Both models predict that during April the bbSOA is the dominant component of bbOA on
314 average over the domain and even if it peaks in South Carolina with high levels in North
315 Carolina and Georgia, it has average concentrations above $0.1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in most areas of the
316 Eastern US (Figure 5a). The alternative scheme predicts that this bbSOA contribution is a factor
317 of 5-10 higher and around or above $1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in the Eastern US. Adding everything together the
318 alternative scheme predicts an average bbOA concentration of $0.3 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ that is a factor of 5
319 higher than the average predicted by the base scheme (Figure 6a).

320 During July, several major wildfires occurred in California and consequently bbOA
321 levels were particularly high in the western US (Figure 2a) reaching levels around $100 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$.
322 This presents a very different situation compared to the spring month discussed above. Once
323 more, the predictions of the two schemes for bbPOA were quite similar (differences less than
324 20%), even if the concentration levels at least in California were much higher. Despite the
325 intensity of the fires in California, the low emissions in the rest of the country resulted in similar
326 average bbPOA levels over the domain as in April ($0.15 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) for both schemes. Both schemes
327 predicted similarly high bbSOA-sv levels with monthly average values up to $15 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and
328 domain average values of $0.2 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ (Figure 2b). The alternative aging scheme predicts high
329 bbSOA-iv that dominate the overall bbOA in the domain with an average of $2 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. The
330 average bbSOA-iv but also the peak levels predicted by the base scheme are more than an order
331 of magnitude lower (Figure 2c). The average bbSOA predicted by the base scheme was
332 approximately a factor of 7 lower (0.3 versus $2 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) for the domain (Figure 5), while the total
333 bbOA was a factor of 5 lower (Figure 6). The differences between the two schemes exceeded 10
334 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ on a monthly average basis over California, and were above $1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ over a large part of
335 the western US (Figure S1).

336 During September there were major wild fires once more in California but also in Oregon
337 (Figure 3). Smaller fires were present in New Mexico and in several southeastern states. The
338 predicted bbPOA average concentration, similar for both schemes, were the lowest of the three
339 simulated periods with a value of approximately $0.1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. The local monthly maxima were 65
340 and $75 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ for the base case and the alternative aging scheme respectively (Figure 3a). The
341 average bbSOA-sv concentration based on the predictions of both schemes were a factor of 6
342 higher (around $0.6 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) than the average bbPOA concentration. The average bbSOA-sv
343 during the month exceeded $0.1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ over a wide region covering most of the western coast of
344 the US and parts of the Pacific. The peak monthly average bbSOA-sv concentration was $7 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$
345 for both simulations. Finally, for the bbSOA-iv the alternative scheme predicted both domain
346 average and peak concentrations that were approximately an order of magnitude higher than the
347 base scheme (Figure 3c). For the base case simulation, bbSOA-iv was as high as $4 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ with a
348 monthly average value of approximately $0.05 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ whereas the same values for the alternative
349 aging scheme were $45 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and $0.7 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ respectively. As a result, the alternative scheme
350 predicts average bbSOA levels that are a factor of 7 higher than the base case (0.1 versus $0.7 \mu\text{g}$
351 m^{-3}) (Figure 5c) and total bbOA levels that are a factor of 4 higher (Figure 6c). For the peak
352 monthly average concentrations, the differences are a factor of 5 for bbSOA and a factor of 1.5
353 for bbOA (given that the bbPOA is a dominant component near the fires).

354

355 **5. Model evaluation with field measurements**

356 The predictions of PMCAMx-SR for daily average $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ OA were compared to the
357 corresponding measurements in 161 Chemical Speciation Network (CSN) sites (located mainly
358 in urban areas) and 162 Interagency Monitoring of Protected Visual Environments (IMPROVE)
359 sites (located mostly in rural and remote areas). These daily average measurements were
360 collected once every three or once every six days and include both the $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ mass concentration
361 and its composition. The organic carbon (OC)/organic aerosol (OA) measurements are used here
362 given our focus on biomass burning OA. The OC of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ aerosol samples collected on quartz
363 fiber filters is measured using thermal optical analysis with the corresponding temperature
364 protocol (Chow et al., 2007). Most measurements were collected in periods during which the
365 corresponding site was not impacted by biomass burning, therefore the use of the complete data
366 set would complicate the interpretation of the evaluation results. To avoid this complication, we

367 have followed Posner et al. (2019) and selected only the periods during which the base case of
368 PMCAMx-SR predicts daily average concentrations higher than a threshold value. Three such
369 thresholds were used to denote all periods with even a low biomass burning impact (threshold
370 $0.1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$), all periods with intermediate or higher impact (threshold $0.5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) and periods
371 with high impact (threshold $1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$). The model prediction for the day and location of the
372 measurement is compared directly against the corresponding measurement.

373 The statistical metrics that were used for the evaluation of the two schemes are the mean
374 bias (MB), the mean absolute gross error (MAGE), the fractional bias (FBIAS), and the
375 fractional error (FERROR) (Fountoukis et al., 2011):

$$376 \quad MB = 1/n \sum_{i=1}^n (P_i - O_i) \quad (3)$$

$$377 \quad MAGE = 1/n \sum_{i=1}^n |P_i - O_i| \quad (4)$$

$$378 \quad FBIAS = 2/n \sum_{i=1}^n (P_i - O_i) / (P_i + O_i) \quad (5)$$

$$379 \quad FERROR = 2/n \sum_{i=1}^n |P_i - O_i| / (P_i + O_i) \quad (6)$$

380 where P_i is the predicted value of the pollutant concentration, O_i is the corresponding observed
381 value and n is the total number of data points used for the comparison.

382 Theodoritsi et al. (2020) have already analyzed the performance of the base scheme of
383 PMCAMx-SR for the same three periods. They concluded that during April the performance of
384 the base scheme is good according to the Morris et al. (2005) criteria and the model tends to
385 underpredict OA (fractional bias -0.16, fractional error 0.51 for the low threshold). PMCAMx-
386 SR showed little bias (3-6%) during July but had a relatively high fractional error (around 55%),
387 so its summer performance was considered average for the periods affected by biomass burning.
388 Finally, the model overpredicted the OA levels in September with the errors increasing when the
389 predicted bbOA concentration increased. This made its performance average to problematic
390 during this period. The metrics of this evaluation by Theodoritsi et al. (2020) for the base case
391 PMCAMx-SR simulation can also be found in Table S1 for completeness.

392 The bbOA predictions of the alternative scheme are in general higher than those of the
393 base scheme. This leads to a small improvement of the performance of PMCAMx-SR during
394 April especially for the low bbOA threshold (Table 2). The model now tends to overpredict OA,
395 while the base scheme underpredicted. For this case, the fractional bias is reduced (in absolute

396 terms) from -0.16 to 0.11 and the fractional error from 0.51 to 0.48. The improvements are minor
397 for the medium threshold, while for the high threshold the fractional bias increases (from -0.14 to
398 0.28) while the fractional error decreases (from 0.53 to 0.5). So overall, the use of the alternative
399 scheme appears to lead to a small improvement of the PMCAMx-SR predictions during this
400 period, but with a tendency towards overprediction especially close to the sources of biomass
401 burning.

402 During July, the base scheme reproduced the OA observations in areas affected by
403 biomass burning with little bias. The alternative scheme predicts a significantly higher SOA-iv
404 production during this period and results in a substantial overprediction of the OA levels in areas
405 with bbOA above all three thresholds (Table 2). The bias increases for the areas closer to the
406 fires (higher threshold). These results strongly suggest that the alternative scheme is too
407 aggressive in the production of SOA-iv during this summertime period with intensive wild fires.

408 PMCAMx-SR using the base scheme has difficulties reproducing the OA concentrations
409 in areas affected by fires. Given that the base scheme already overpredicts OA levels, the
410 increased SOA-iv predicted by the alternative scheme leads to additional deterioration of the
411 model performance. The alternative scheme substantially overpredicts OA and the fractional bias
412 increases closer to the sources of biomass burning. Overall, the performance of the alternative
413 scheme during September is like that during July.

414

415 **6. Importance of the VBS parameters used in the two bbOA schemes**

416 The difference in the IVOC emissions and aging schemes appears to explain a large
417 fraction of the differences in the predictions of the two schemes in the simulated periods.
418 However, there are other potentially important differences in the parameters used in the two
419 schemes. These different parameters include the enthalpy of vaporization and the molecular
420 weights of the various bbOA components. The effect of these together with the effect of the
421 assumed volatility distributions of the emitted bbOA components and the assumed aging
422 schemes was investigated. Sensitivity tests were performed for one of the three periods (April
423 2008) to quantify the individual effect of these parameters on the predictions of PMCAMx-SR.
424 The results of these tests and their comparison with the base case results are analyzed in the
425 subsequent sections.

426

427 **6.1 Enthalpy of vaporization**

428 In this first sensitivity test, we changed the effective enthalpies of vaporization of the
429 bbOA components (bbPOA, bbSOA-sv, bbSOA-iv) in the base scheme from their original values
430 that varied from 64 to 106 kJ mol⁻¹ to those of the alternative scheme (Table 1). The new values
431 were equal to 35 kJ mol⁻¹ for the bbSOA components and varied from 37 to 70 kJ mol⁻¹ for the
432 bbPOA. This test allows us to quantify the importance of the significantly lower enthalpies used
433 in the alternative scheme based on the work of Ciarelli et al. (2017a, b). All other parameters of
434 the base scheme were kept the same.

435 The changes in the predictions of the model were small, a few percent or less (Figure S2).
436 The use of the higher original enthalpies of vaporization resulted in a little higher concentration
437 for all bbOA components. The maximum monthly average changes were 0.3 µg m⁻³ for bbPOA,
438 0.03 µg m⁻³ for bbPOA-sv, 0.03 µg m⁻³ bbSOA-iv and 0.4 µg m⁻³ for total bbOA all near
439 Savannah, Georgia. However, for most of the US the change in total bbOA was less than 0.05 µg
440 m⁻³. Therefore, the major differences in bbSOA-iv predictions of the base and alternative scheme
441 were not due to their different enthalpies of vaporization.

442

443 **6.2 Molecular weights**

444 The base scheme assumes a molecular weight of 250 g mol⁻¹ for all bbOA components
445 while a range of molecular weights from 113 to 216 g mol⁻¹ are used in the alternative scheme
446 (Table 1). These variable molecular weights are also intended to account for fragmentation
447 effects and are accompanied by a stoichiometric coefficient equal to unity (instead of 1.075 in
448 the base scheme). We replaced the molecular weights of the base scheme with those of the
449 alternative, changed the stoichiometric coefficients in the aging reactions from 1.075 to 1, kept
450 everything else the same, and repeated the April simulation.

451 The impact of these changes in the molecular weight values and stoichiometric
452 coefficients was small (Figure 7). The maximum concentration changes for the monthly average
453 concentrations were 0.02 µg m⁻³ for bbPOA, 0.03 µg m⁻³ for bbSOA-sv, 0.1 µg m⁻³ for bbPOA-iv
454 and 0.1 µg m⁻³ for total bbOA all in the borders between South Carolina and Georgia. The use of
455 the Ciarelli et al. (2017) parameters (molecular weights and aging stoichiometric coefficients)
456 led to very small reductions of the bbPOA and bbSOA-sv levels and small increases in the
457 bbSOA-iv levels. The latter dominated the overall bbOA change which increased by 0.01 to 0.03

458 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in large parts of the Eastern US and by 0.03-0.1 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in South Carolina and Georgia.
459 These changes are still only a few percent. This small impact of the changes is partially due to
460 the fact that they cancel each other to a large extent. The decrease in molecular weights leads to
461 increased partitioning towards the particle phase and therefore higher bbOA levels, where the
462 decrease in the aging stoichiometric coefficients has the opposite effect for the secondary
463 components.

464

465 **6.3 Volatility distribution of biomass burning emissions**

466 In this test, the emissions of the various organic compounds in the VBS from biomass
467 burning were changed from these of the base scheme to those of Ciarelli et al. (2017) (Table 1).
468 This change does not affect the LVOC emissions and the SVOC emissions for C* less or equal
469 than $10^2 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. However, it increases the emissions of the $10^3 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ volatility bin (by adding to
470 these emissions those that are in the $10^4 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ bin) and also increases significantly the
471 emissions of the IVOCs in the $10^6 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ while it zeros those in the $10^5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ bin.

472 The use of the Ciarelli et al. (2017) volatility distributions leads to significant changes of
473 the predicted bbOA concentration levels (Figure 8). In all areas, and for all bbOA components it
474 predicts higher concentrations. The maximum concentration differences between the two
475 simulations were $0.1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ for bbPOA, $0.1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ for bbSOA-sv and $1.5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ for bbSOA-iv.
476 These differences are quite similar in magnitude to those of the base and alternative schemes
477 (Figure 4a). This strongly suggests that the differences in the assumed bbOA volatility-resolved
478 emissions is mainly responsible for the differences in the bbOA predictions of the two schemes.
479 For example, for the average total bbOA in the modeling domain the change in the volatility
480 distributions led to an increase of the base case results by $0.14 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. This should be compared
481 with the $0.2 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ that is the difference between the average bbOA predicted by the base and
482 alternative schemes.

483 The most important difference is the change in the IVOC emissions resulting in
484 significant changes of the bbSOA-iv. The predicted bbSOA-iv of PMCAMx-SR with the base
485 scheme using the default and the Ciarelli et al. (2017) bbOA volatility distributions are depicted
486 in Figure 9. The monthly maximum concentration was predicted to be 0.2 and $1.5 \mu\text{m m}^{-3}$ for the
487 base case and the alternative bbOA scheme respectively in South Carolina. This is also

488 consistent, with our conclusion that the difference in the IVOC emissions is the leading cause of
489 the differences of the predictions of the base and alternative schemes.

490

491 **7. Conclusions**

492 An alternative bbOA scheme based on the work of Ciarelli et al. (2017a, b) has been used
493 in PMCAMx-SR to quantify the impact of bbOA on ambient particulate matter levels across the
494 continental U.S during April, July and September 2008. The alternative parameterization was
495 originally developed based on residential heating biomass burning experiments (i.e. combustion
496 in stoves). In this study we test its applicability for the simulation of the bbOA from other
497 sources (wildfires, prescribed and agricultural burning) in different periods.

498 The alternative scheme predicts in general much higher bbOA levels than the baseline
499 scheme for all seasons. Both schemes suggest that secondary production is a major process for
500 the average bbOA levels over the US in all examined periods. However, the alternative scheme
501 predicts that the production of secondary aerosol from intermediate volatility organic compounds
502 emitted during biomass burning is a factor of 5-10 higher than that of the base scheme. The
503 differences in the predictions of the other bbOA components (primary bbOA and bbOA from
504 semivolatile compounds) are low to modest.

505 A set of sensitivity tests showed that the most important difference between the two
506 schemes is the assumed emission rate of intermediate volatility organic compounds together with
507 their oxidation to form secondary organic aerosol. The impact of other different parameters,
508 including the assumed enthalpies of vaporization and molecular weights was small.

509 The performance of PMCAMx-SR using the two schemes was evaluated against
510 observed values obtained from 161 CSN and 162 IMPROVE network measurement sites across
511 the US. During April the use of the alternative scheme leads to a small improvement of the
512 performance of PMCAMx-SR. However, during the more photochemically active periods of July
513 and September, with intense wild fires the PMCAMx-SR performance for OA deteriorates when
514 the alternative scheme is used instead of the base scheme. This strongly suggests that the
515 production of SOA-iv under these conditions is too aggressive. Fragmentation reactions may
516 become more important under these conditions leading to lower production of secondary organic
517 aerosol Our analysis suggests that the alternative scheme could be used during the spring-like

518 conditions, but it should probably be avoided during summer-like periods characterized by
519 intensive wild-fires activities.

520 The alternative scheme considered here has been derived based on experiments using
521 residential heating emissions. An assumption used in most biomass burning OA simulation
522 efforts so far is that the same parameterization can be used for the different burning types:
523 wildfires, agricultural burning, residential heating, prescribed burning, etc. Our work provides
524 some support to the hypothesis that different parameterizations may be needed for residential
525 heating and wildfires. This is clearly an issue that deserves additional attention in future
526 modeling efforts.

527
528 *Code availability:* The PMCAMx-SRv1.0 code is available in Zenodo in [https://](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4071362)
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530 *Data availability:* The data in the study are available from the authors upon request
531 (spyros@chemeng.upatras.gr).

532 *Author contributions:* GNT wrote the code, conducted the simulations, analysed the results, and
533 wrote the paper. GC contributed to the design of the code, analysis of the results, and the writing
534 of the paper. SNP was responsible for the design of the study, the synthesis of the results and
535 contributed to the writing of the paper.

536 *Competing interests.* The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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539
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726

727 **Table 1.** Parameters used to simulate bbPOA, bbSOA-sv and bbSOA-iv in PMCAMx-SR.

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C^* at 298 K ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	10^{-1}	10^0	10^1	10^2	10^3	10^4	10^5	10^6
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Base Scheme

	Fraction of bbPOA emissions	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.3	0.25	0.25
ΔH (kJ mol^{-1})	bbPOA, bbSOA-sv, bbSOA-iv	106	100	94	88	82	76	70	64
MW (g mol^{-1})	bbPOA, bbSOA-sv, bbSOA-iv	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250

Alternative bbOA scheme

	Fraction of bbPOA emissions	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.4	0	0	4.75
ΔH (kJ mol^{-1})	bbPOA	-	70	59	48	37	-	-	64
	bbSOA-sv	35	35	35	35	35	35	35	35
	bbSOA-iv	35	35	35	35	35	35	35	35
MW (g mol^{-1})	bbPOA	216	216	216	216	215	215	215	113
	bbSOA-sv	194	189	184	179	179	179	179	179
	bbSOA-iv	149	144	140	135	131	131	131	131

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Table 2. PMCAMx-SR alternative scheme OA prediction skill metrics against observed values from CSN and IMPROVE networks at biomass-impacted sites.

	# Measur.	Mean Observed ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	Mean Predicted ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	MB ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	MAGE ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	FBIAS	FERROR
bbOA > 0.1 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$							
April	538	4.51	4.7	0.19	2.18	0.11	0.48
July	1168	5.14	11.78	6.64	7.72	0.59	0.75
September	937	3.45	6.61	3.16	4.44	0.60	0.77
bbOA > 0.5 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$							
April	163	6.29	7.43	1.14	3.07	0.21	0.45
July	468	6.46	20.32	13.85	14.64	0.97	1.01
September	270	4.45	11.90	7.45	9.38	0.85	0.98
bbOA > 1 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$							
April	53	7.91	10.22	2.31	4.41	0.28	0.50
July	311	8.20	27.04	18.85	19.86	1.03	1.08
September	150	4.23	16.73	12.50	13.14	1.03	1.10

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(a) Fresh bbPOA

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(b) bbSOA-sv

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(c) bbSOA-iv

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765 **Figure 1:** PMCAMx-SR predicted ground – level concentrations of (a) fresh bbPOA, (b) SV-
766 bbSOA-sv and (c) SV-bbSOA-iv from all biomass burning sources during April 2008. Left
767 column refers to the base case simulations and right column to the simulations with the
768 alternative bbOA scheme. All concentrations are in $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$.

769

(a) Fresh bbPOA

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(b) bbSOA-sv

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(c) bbSOA-iv

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778 **Figure 2:** PMCAMx-SR predicted ground – level concentrations of (a) fresh bbPOA, (b) SV-
779 bbSOA-sv and (c) SV-bbSOA-iv from all biomass burning sources during July 2008. Left
780 column refers to the base case simulations and right column to the simulations with the
781 alternative bbOA scheme. All concentrations are in $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$.

782

(a) Fresh bbPOA

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(b) bbSOA-sv

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(c) bbSOA-iv

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791 **Figure 3:** PMCAMx-SR predicted ground – level concentrations of (a) fresh bbPOA, (b) SV-
792 bbSOA-sv and (c) SV-bbSOA-iv from all biomass burning sources during September 2008. Left
793 column refers to the base case simulations and right column to the simulations with the
794 alternative bbOA scheme. All concentrations are in $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$.

(a) April

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(b) July

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(c) September

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803 **Figure 4:** Average predicted absolute ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) difference (alternative aging scheme minus base
804 case) of ground-level $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ bbPOA, bbSOA-sv and bbSOA-iv concentrations from PMCAMx-
805 SR base case and alternative aging scheme simulations during the modeled periods. Positive
806 values indicate that the PMCAMx-SR alternative aging scheme simulations predicts higher
807 concentrations.

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(a) April

Base case

Alternative bbOA scheme

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818

(b) July

Base case

Alternative bbOA scheme

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820

(c) September

Base case

Alternative bbOA scheme

822

823 **Figure 5:** PMCAMx-SR predicted ground – level concentrations of bbSOA-sv and bbSOA-iv
824 from all biomass burning sources during (a) April, (b) July and (c) September 2008. Left
825 column refers to the base case simulations and right column to the simulations with the
826 alternative bbOA scheme. All concentrations are in $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$.
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Base case (a) April Alternative bbOA scheme

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Base case (b) July Alternative bbOA scheme

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(c) September

Base case Alternative bbOA scheme

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837 **Figure 6:** PMCAMx-SR predicted ground – level concentrations of bbOA from all biomass
838 burning sources during (a) April, (b) July and (c) September 2008. Left column refers to the
839 base case simulations and right column to the simulations with the alternative bbOA scheme.
840 All concentrations are in $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$.

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846 **Figure 7:** Average predicted increase ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) of the predictions of the base PMCAM_x-SR
847 scheme when the molecular weights and aging stoichiometric coefficient of Ciarelli et al (2017)
848 are used compared to the predictions with the default values for ground-level PM_{2.5} (a) bbPOA,
849 (b) bbSOA-sv (c) bbSOA-iv and (d) bbOA during April 2008. Positive values indicate that the
850 PMCAM_x-SR base scheme with the molecular weights/stoichiometric coefficients of Ciarelli et
851 al. (2017) predicts higher concentrations.

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862 **Figure 8:** Average predicted increase ($\mu g m^{-3}$) of the predictions of the base PMCAMx-SR
863 scheme when the volatility distribution Ciarelli et al (2017) is used for the biomass burning
864 emissions compared to the predictions with the default values for ground-level $PM_{2.5}$ (a) bbPOA,
865 (b) bbSOA-sv (c) bbSOA-iv and (d) bbOA during April 2008. Positive values indicate that the
866 PMCAMx-SR base scheme with the volatility distribution of Ciarelli et al. (2017) predicts higher
867 concentrations.

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Figure 9: PMCAMx-SR predicted ground – level concentrations ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) of bbSOA-iv for the base scheme using (a) the base-case volatility distribution and (b) the Ciarelli et al. (2017) volatility distribution.